

CONTEMPORARY TRENDS IN LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15865768>

Annotation. This article is about modern landscape design.

Keywords: design, landscape, architecture, industry, practical experience.

Based on the rich experience of the past, possessing the entire arsenal of compositional and technical techniques developed by previous generations, modern architects are confidently moving forward. The practical experience and development trends of modern landscape architecture can be defined in several directions: - a natural environment for recreation and walks, which is largely formed artificially and takes its origins in the gardening art of antiquity - these are multifunctional parks, exhibition gardens, sports and Olympic park complexes, zoos and botanical gardens, memorial parks, museum gardens, children's and amusement parks for entertainment, private gardens, all kinds of recreational facilities;

- special-purpose green areas are a system of urban greening, i.e. squares, parks, boulevards, embankments, pedestrian zones, gardens near public buildings and in residential buildings, as well as all kinds of urban planning landscape complexes, nurseries, cemeteries, protective and meliorative plantings, flat structures; - gardens on artificial foundations, placed on platforms, roofs of various structures or in interiors; - reclamation or restoration of disturbed and exhausted landscapes; - restoration, reconstruction and conservation of monuments of landscape gardening art;

- creation of communications in nature and urban environments - these are roads, bridges, viaducts, transport service stations, as well as canals, product pipelines and power lines, which differ in length.

The objects of architectural and landscape design include: - landscape objects of populated areas - water-green systems, open urban spaces, residential development environment, industrial complex environment, protective green zones; - recreational objects - gardens and parks, forest parks, a system of recreation and tourism facilities, short-term recreation areas, long-term recreation areas, health resort areas, parkways, tourist routes;

8 - territories of specially protected landscapes - reserves and sanctuaries, national parks, cultural and historical zones, protected zones of natural monuments; - objects of various economic purposes - water protection zones, landscape corridors of communications, melioration and mining zones, agricultural territories.

Another classification divides landscape objects into two large groups - these are the main and special objects of landscape design.

The main objects of landscape design include: - urban multifunctional (culture and recreation) and specialized gardens and parks (children's, amusement, sports, memorial, exhibition, zoological, botanical, etc.); - suburban areas of mass recreation.

Special objects of landscape design include: - gardens at public buildings; - gardens in residential buildings; - gardens on artificial foundations; - squares, boulevards, pedestrian spaces; - nurseries, cemeteries, protective and meliorative plantings.

Modern landscape architecture, based on historical experience, has made great strides over the past hundred years. Distinctive features of modern landscape art are: - connection of park space with urban development; - expansion of the range of park structures; - development of parks of various types - multifunctional, specialized, large suburban and mini-parks; - emergence of new gardens related to technical capabilities - roof gardens, indoor gardens; - park construction as a method of land reclamation; - large-scale earthworks, use of geoplastics and land art;

2 Geoplastics is the artificial creation or modification of relief. It is a promising direction in landscape architecture and is a type of vertical planning, which mainly pursues artistic goals.

Modern technology allows you to create almost any relief. 3 Land art - (from the English land art - landscape art), a movement in art that arose in the United States in the late 1960s, in which the work created by the artist is inextricably linked with the natural landscape. In land art works, the landscape was used as a form and means of creating a work. Often, works are performed in open spaces, where they are exposed to natural

9 - intensive solution of transport problems; - formation of new methods of creating artificial landscapes; - formation and preservation of the natural park environment or creation of its appearance artificially.

In the second half - the end of the 20th century, a new type of garden appears, different from the previous ones. It absorbed both traditionalism and international influences. Glass, metal and synthetic materials penetrated the garden just as they found their way into other areas of visual art. A new tendency appeared to impose a distinct human trace on nature.

Thus, another characteristic feature of modern landscape art is the combination and mixing of styles, the integration of concepts, design techniques, elements and approaches to the organization of space. The process of globalization, which has influenced modern park construction and landscape architecture, can be considered as an opportunity for the interpenetration of cultural traditions, which, in general, has a positive effect. It has not led to the creation of uniform, "unified" territories, which many specialists fear.

On the contrary, we see an original landscape environment, where national traditions of different countries of the world are not only preserved, but also enriched. The use of various techniques (Italian, French, Arabic, English, Chinese, Japanese, etc.) in modern landscape objects creates a balance of architecture and picturesqueness, regularity and landscape.

Features of park construction in large and largest cities: - limitation of park areas forces us to search for spatial and visual relationships between urban structures and park environment; - satisfaction of various tastes implies creation of multifunctional parks with corresponding territorial zoning and careful development of park use regime.

As examples that effectively demonstrate the possibilities of geoplastics and land art, we can consider the gardens created according to the projects of the famous American architect, C. Jencks - "Cosmic Reflections", "Jupiter", "What is Life?", "Northern Goddess", the park area of the Scottish National Gallery of Modern Art.

Fantastic landscapes amaze the imagination with the winding lines of the terraced relief, reflecting ponds, original sculptural forms that are the basis of the composition.

They are characterized by harmony of scale and style with the surrounding area. While working on the projects, Jencks was inspired by fractal geometry, philosophy and reflected on the meaning of life and the Universe. - specialized parks are created, differentiated by the functions of use (children's, sports, exhibition, memorial, etc.); - the multifunctional profile of parks requires the placement of a system of internal roads (as a rule, pedestrian and transport routes are separated);

- the formation of a park environment is developing in two directions - this is the formation of a clearly artificial landscape with unusual forms, which is typical for multifunctional parks and, on the contrary, the creation of a natural park environment, close in nature to the natural landscape; - in technical and professional terms, a high level of development of the territory is characteristic of park objects abroad.

As you can see, the range of problems and issues solved by landscape architecture is very wide, and the knowledge of only an architect or urban planner is often not enough. When creating a landscape object, many specialists of various profiles are involved and actively cooperate: engineers, ecologists, soil scientists, biologists, geologists, hydrologists and hydraulic engineers, climatologists, etc. Landscape thinking, along with urban planning and volumetric-spatial thinking, should become a necessary condition for architectural creativity.

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